

FRAMING KINSHIP: THE CASE OF PORTUGUESE ENTAILS (MORGADIOS AND CAPELAS), 14TH-17TH CENTURIES

*Configurando el parentesco: el caso de los vínculos portugueses
(morgadios y capellanías), siglos XIV-XVII*

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ABSTRACT: This article focuses on the kinship relationships framed by entails in Portugal, between the 14th and 17th centuries. Why did the founders decide to establish entails, and how did they think this solution would protect their kinship groups? What kind of organisation did they imagine and intend to implement for future relatives? How did they try to constrain the behaviour of their relatives and their relationships? Did entails shape a type of specific kinship organisation? Based primarily on foundational documents, but also resorting to judicial documentation, we analyse the schemes of succession and the formation of kinship hotspots within broader parental structures. Furthermore, we analyse the founder's determination to regulate and constrain kinship relations through the key notion of corporate hierarchy of inequality.

Keywords: kinship; founders; entails; morgadios; capelas.

RESUMEN: Este artículo se centra en las relaciones de parentesco enmarcadas por las fundaciones de vínculos en Portugal, entre los siglos XIV y XVII. ¿Por qué los fundadores decidieron crear los vínculos y cómo

consideraron que esta solución protegía a sus grupos de parentesco? ¿Qué tipo de organización imaginaban, y pretendían poner en práctica, para los futuros parientes? ¿Cómo intentaron condicionar el comportamiento de sus parientes y las relaciones entre ellos? ¿Es posible discernir la formación de tipos específicos de organizaciones de parentesco moldeados por los vínculos? Partiendo principalmente de documentos fundacionales, pero recurriendo también a documentación judicial, se analizan los esquemas sucesorios y la formación de núcleos de parentesco dentro de estructuras parentales más amplias. Además, se analiza la voluntad de los fundadores de regular y condicionar las relaciones de parentesco a través de la clave interpretativa de una jerarquización corporativa de la desigualdad.

Palabras clave: parentesco; fundadores; vínculos; mayorazgos; capelas.

1. INTRODUCTION

On 10 June 1541, in a house in Rua Nova, the most prestigious street in Porto, three close relatives gathered for a common purpose. The house belonged to Luís Álvares de Madureira, *fidalgo da casa do rei* and member of one of the most important lineages of the city (Brito, 1997, pp. 106-107, 368). With him were Joana de Madureira (his wife and cousin) and their aunt Isabel de Madureira. Together, they instituted a *morgado*, a familial corporate body (Rosa, 2020) and a form of entail that was specifically Iberian (Abreu, 2001-2002, pp. 337-338; Rosa, 2012, pp. 596-609)¹. After repeatedly postponing the division of the inheritance, they aimed to entail their assets in the service of God and to preserve the Madureira lineage's memory, thus fulfilling the wish of the ancestors from whom they had inherited the estates. The entail was presented as a way to preserve the family's memory, kinship ties and social status, which according to this line of reasoning would disintegrate through the constant partition and sharing of estates, no matter how substantial. Even when entails benefited the eldest son, they created a strong pole within the parental universe. In times of hardship, siblings could turn to this benefited relative for support. For this reason, the founders argued that entails «were ordained by the ancients according to divine and human law»².

1. We will employ the concept of entails covering both *morgados* and *capelas*.

2. We know of this set of documents from copies of the *Registo Vincular do Distrito do Porto*. These records were created as a response to an 1860 governmental decree stipulating the abolition of all entails not registered within two years (Esteves, 2008: 53-59). The documents relating to the entail in question were presented by the administrator Francisco Diogo de Sousa Cirne de Madureira. Their origin may lie in a «livro do morgadio», although they were

The founding document extensively regulated the institution, moulding the profile of the heir, who was recruited within consanguineous kinship structures, until the end of time, ideally along vertical lines of succession («linha direita»). The heir would be the first-born male child, a layman, loyal to the king, and physically and mentally healthy. Since the entail was intended to ensure the perpetuation of the lineage, both through its members and its symbols of identity, the surname Madureira and the use of the founder's coat of arms were imposed on the administrators.

The institution was further shaped in the following years. In 1559 and 1560, Luís Álvares and Joana entailed the inheritance of Pedro de Madureira, Joana's father, and their «terça»³. They also added regulatory clauses that constrained the heirs' behaviour and moulded kinship relationships: they specified the right to remove an heir from the line of succession if they married without their father's consent and forced the administrators to live in Porto or its outskirts, unless the king's service took them elsewhere. The couple's son was also ordered to reach an understanding with the monastery where his sisters would enter as nuns, such that their inheritances would be incorporated into the entail since those assets «belonged to their grandparents and great-grandparents».

One of the clauses imposed by the founders was the obligation to produce a book of the entail. The copies of this document, which had to be made of good paper and bear the founder's coat of arms, would contain the essential documents for management purposes, including the foundation deed and documents concerning the estates. The Madureira family's genealogy — originating in Bragança and tracing the surname back to the «quinta» of Madureira — was also recorded. Fleeing from a murder charge, Álvaro Eanes de Madureira came to Porto, married «a rich and honourable widow», and began a process of social ascension. The institution of the entail was seen as a pivotal moment in this history: rising to social prominence, the entail linked past, present, and future through kinship relationships.

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This case and the various points raised — the endogamous marriages, the postponement of partitions, the founding of the entail in fulfilment of the ancestors'

probably not transcribed in the same order as that of the source document. The set of documents (including the foundation deed, partitions and declaration deeds, and other documents) is recorded in: *Francisco Diogo de Sousa Madureira, escritura da instituição de vários vínculos de que é cabeça a capela de Nossa Senhora da Misericórdia na quinta do Freixo, freguesia de Guilhabreu*, 24 January 1863, Porto, Arquivo Distrital do Porto (ADP), Governo Civil do Porto, Registo de Vínculos, C/4/1/3 - 4806, Fols. 173-274.

3. In Portuguese legislation, individuals could dispose of a third of their assets if they had legitimate heirs.

wishes — demonstrate a collective coordination to strengthen a kinship group defined around a common identity. The entail and its estates gave substance to kinship, forming a scheme of relations among relatives based on a corporate hierarchy of inequality, a concept whose relevance and operability we will discuss in this article. By establishing a corporate entity, the founders intended to mould relationships in order to produce unity and perpetuity through the entailed assets, laying down rules in the founding document's clauses (Rosa, 2020). The founders thus established themselves as pillars and references for adopted behaviour, constraining future generations. Their wishes, converted into the «internal laws» of the entails (Rosa, 1995, pp. 221-222), were also the references for resolving conflicts when they eventually arose.

The founders' power was therefore perpetually projected onto future generations. During the long period until the dismemberment of entails (initiated with the Marquis of Pombal's laws in the mid-18th century and concluded with their definitive abolition in 1863), profound social transformations produced such deep ruptures that many of the conceptual foundations that governed the societies in which entails existed, and in which these institutions were fully coherent, eventually disappeared. The power of the founders over future generations and the corporate hierarchy of inequality that marked these kinship relationships were deeply contested by the triumphant liberal elites (Esteves, 2008, pp. 32-96). Alexandre Herculano, one of the heroes of the victorious camp in the 1832-1834 civil war, is well known for his invective against entails: «The founder of an entail has done nothing more than pile up the bodies of individuals from various generations and placed upon them a throne to his vanity» (Herculano, 1983, pp. 335-336).

Considering the depth of these social transformations, a 21st century observer faces a world of possible misunderstandings regarding the founders, their heirs and the people who lived within the framework of entails. In this article, we attempt to reconstruct the logic behind the founding of entails, with a special focus on kinship as one of the essential components of these corporate entities: why did the founders decide to establish entails, and how did they think this solution would protect their kinship groups? What kind of organisation did they imagine and intend to implement for future relatives? How did they try to constrain the behaviour of their relatives and their relationships? In short, did entails frame and mould a specific kinship organisation during the centuries they were in force and deeply embedded in social organisation?

2. THE SAMPLE AND THE DOCUMENTS

To answer these questions, a documentary corpus was constructed primarily based on founding documents, since it was through these instruments that the

institutors sought to outline the profile of these corporate bodies. Subsidiarily, other documentary typologies, such as the vast corpus of judicial sentences were also used to enrich the investigation. This documentation allows for surveys of the conflictual dimension of entails, and of how the founder's constraints upon subsequent generations operated and were received.

Entails could be established through different types of documents: foundation deeds, wills, codicils, donations, and dowry deeds. The metaphor of a «documentary landscape» is very useful to reflect on the materials we can gather for our research purpose. A landscape has specific characteristics an observer can describe. It is not immutable; rather, it is shaped by forces and agents that act on it. The usefulness of this metaphor lies in the extent to which it provokes the historian to reflect on the traces that have come down to us from the past. Today, these traces form a landscape with a different configuration than at the time when these elements were created. Historians, and especially specialists in ancient societies — in this case, pre-modern European societies — work with fragments of a vanished world. Moreover, before being considered historical documents, these fragments were instruments produced for specific purposes, giving expression to social relations. In short, the disappearance of a world implies that the fragments it leaves behind are fewer than those it produced and, above all, the type of social relations these vestiges embodied have profoundly changed, or even disappeared (Morsel, 2000, 2004b; Kuchenbuch, 2004; Anheim, 2011; Rosa, 2017). In what concerns entails, the «documentary landscape» is largely composed of fragments shattered by the abolition dictated in 1863. Founding documents are mostly accessible through copies preserved in the archives of the Crown and the Church's *Ancien Régime* institutions that exercised arbitration or surveillance over entails⁴.

This article is based on a sample of around 700 institutional documents produced between the 14th and 17th centuries. This vast corpus allows us to discern the major trends in the organisation of kinship relations conceived by the founders, from a diachronic perspective. Within this universe, a specific set of more complete and detailed documents would allow us to investigate how the founders justified establishing the entails and provide data to frame and understand major trends, as well as the less regular discernible variants. These more detailed documents, although distributed throughout the chronology, are largely from the 16th and 17th centuries, an era of massive increase in entail foundations. The founders who most fully explained their decisions usually belonged to dominant groups, both lay and ecclesiastical. They were frequently people connected to the royal court and its

4. A characterisation of the documentary typologies and the institutional universe related to entails can be found in the *Vinculum Information System Guide*: <https://visg.vinculum.fcsh.unl.pt/en/>.

judicial and administrative structures, such as knights and lawyers; and they were regularly linked to the Portuguese crown's military and commercial enterprises in its overseas territories. One can often find top ecclesiastical figures, such as canons and bishops. As in the opening case of the Madureira lineage, this broader sample indicates that the institution of the entail often accompanies or culminates a process of upward mobility, organising kinship according to a representation of what is considered appropriate for elite groups.

The research questions, the sample, and the documentary corpus followed a different chronological perspective than the traditional academic division between the Middle Ages and the early modern period. Rather, this research followed a chronologic arch from the appearance of entails, in the 14th century, to its very large diffusion in the 16th and 17th centuries. This perspective does not deny some profound transformations in Portuguese society during this vast period but argues that a rational and sustained comprehension of how entails affected social structures must be analysed in a broader chronological perspective, while considering diachronic transformations and each century's specific contexts. In this respect, we are deepening the practice of Spanish and Portuguese historians whose research has focused on topics such as family and aristocratic groups. These include Juan Hernández Franco, Enrique Soria Mesa, Mafalda Soares da Cunha and Nuno Gonçalo Monteiro, all of whom are cited in this article. Specialists of the early modern period, they tend to start their work in the 15th century, a pivotal period for the construction of the main structures that would characterize Iberian societies until the end of *Ancien Régime*. In our research, the 14th century appears as the starting point since that was when entails started to be founded in Portugal.

3. AN ENTAILMENT KINSHIP

Which characteristics can be attributed to the entailment kinship? On the one hand, the founders selected the descendants and collaterals within the universe of relatives, at the time of the foundation and in the future and defined specific perimeters for the recruitment of administrators to ensure the continuity of the entail and the memory its founders. On the other hand, these perimeters were constrained by a diverse set of clauses and institutional mechanisms that regulated the administrators' behaviour, as well as their relationship with their relatives. In short, by defining perimeters and regulating social conduct, the founders sought to shape kinship groups.

The basic idea behind the founder's choice was the belief in the power of entails to generate unity and appease conflicts. When Fernando Gonçalves de Baião and Inês Gonçalves established their entail in Tavira, in 1470, they emphasised that one of the estates had given rise to hatreds and disputes between relatives due to its

division, which would not have happened had it been owned by «a single person as in a *morgado*»⁵. Through the concentration of assets and their entailment, group cohesion could be generated, thus preventing the disintegration resulting from the constant division of inheritances and fading of kinship ties. Their conviction, shared by entail and fideicommissum foundations in various parts of *Ancien Régime* Europe, was that estates gave substance to kinship (Haddad 2012), designing and maintaining corporate bodies within the universe of kinship structures operating a coincidence between people and family assets with juridical specificities (Rosa, 2019, p. 266), and ensuring the preservation of the memory of those who gathered the estates and the fulfilment of their «desire to last» (Molénat, 1986; Lemeunier, 1993; Irigoyen, 2004). In 1389, a founder belonging to the upper echelons of the aristocracy, Diogo Lopes Pacheco, declared that the memory of men was ensured «by perpetuating their estates in their children and in their lineage» (Dias, 2005a, pp. 67-71). In 1591, António Cordovil emphasised that, without entails, there were no «estates that could always bring to mind the person and the name of the person who left and gathered them»⁶. The foundation prevented the squandering of assets, preserved the memory of the ancestors, and served as a pole of support for relatives. In *Ancien Régime* society, such institutions also affirmed and reinforced the power of the founder (Rosa, 2020), a figure whose importance can be glimpsed in multiple realities (the founders of kingdoms, of churches), some closely related to the dominant representations in the social groups that instituted entails, such as the more or less mythologised founders of noble lineages, figures also crystallised in medieval genealogical literature whose fortune would deepen in the increasingly aristocratic spirit of the early modern period.

3.1. *To carve and prune*

The founders defined the preferred perimeter of relatives that would succeed them, throughout generations, from within the field of consanguineous kinship. The nomination of people whose primary relationship, as indicated in the documents, was that of *criado* or godchild was very rare⁷, but still significant, illustrating the

5. *Entail foundation deed by Fernando Gonçalves de Baião and Inês Gonçalves*, 26 October 1470, Torre do Tombo (=TT), Lisbon, Leitura Nova, lv. 11, Fols. 1-1v.

6. *Will of António Cordovil*, 2 August 1591, TT, Lisbon, Arquivo do Arquivo, Livros de Registo, lv. 46, Fols. 332-337.

7. Among several examples of this small set of foundations involving baptismal kinship and *criados*, present throughout the chronology: the entail founded by Maria de Matos Bettencourt in Madeira in 1680 for her goddaughter, Mother Catarina de Jesus, and her father, António Moniz Furtado (*Will of Maria de Matos Bettencourt*, 11 December 1680, TT, Lisbon, Morgados e Capelas, Registos Vinculares, Ponta Delgada, 20, Fols. 154-162); the entail established

variety of solutions that could be employed. Sons or nephews were the first to be called as heirs. After the first administrator, the field of recruitment in succeeding generations was based on consanguineous kinship⁸, forming «discrete groups» (Barry et al, 2000, p. 725)⁹, in line with the conceptualisations of the anthropology of kinship, or a basis from which to resort to an «operational kinship» (Rosa, 1995, pp. 96-97, 100-101; Morsel, 2004a; 2017, 58-75). This field is that of «linhagem» and «geração»¹⁰ terms used over the centuries by the founders about their parental universe, and upon which they imposed mechanisms to define proximities and distances, preferences and exclusions.

The most regular scheme — catalogued in this way by the 16th and 17th centuries jurists who typified the casuistry of entails (Clavero, 1974, pp. 211-221; Teixeira, 2003; Cabral, 2019) — was that of primogeniture and masculinity, based on representations well rooted in medieval and early modern societies. Firstly, male primacy, or the «androcentrism» described by Melero Muñoz (Melero Muñoz, 2019), that tends to naturalize the concentration of power and wealth within the hands of men; women in these conditions were exceptions, usually associated with widowhood (Aguiar, 2022a)¹¹. Secondly, the dominance of seniors over cadets, fostered by the representations of greater similarity and love between fathers and their first-born sons. This notion was partly taken from the succession mechanisms of the Iberian crowns, whose doctrinal justifications can be found at least since the

by Beatriz Rodrigues in Estremoz in 1495, appointing her *criados*, or servants, Afonso Eanes and João Marques as the first administrators (*Extract of Beatriz Rodrigues' will*, 15 October 1495, TT, Lisbon, Feitos da Coroa, Núcleo Antigo 276, Fols. 170-171).

8. Only when this preferential universe failed would other entities outside the consanguineous family play a role. In this circumstance, the king was called upon to choose an administrator, or the administration would be left to an institution, including municipalities, brotherhoods, and convents.

9. In other words, descent groups that sought to perpetuate themselves and act as moral persons («corporate groups»), passing on material and immaterial assets, rights, and duties. Although the conceptualisation of these social formations was designed for bilinear kinship systems (and not for complex and undifferentiated filiation systems, like the European), there are some similarities with entailment kinship: despite the global scope of individual kinship relationships, the entailment framework would certainly frame perceptions and representations of kinship networks differently, as well as social behaviours and their reciprocal surveillance by groups.

10. The terms are used both in the sense of a kinship group and of relationships between individuals.

11. In the Portuguese context, especially in aristocratic milieus, single women were a very rare exception. Tendentially, widowhood was when women came to control significant portions of wealth, recovering their dowries and amassing the dowers promised by the husband's families. Sometimes, entails' founders specifically imposed that the entail's estates and/or revenues could not be used to finance dowries or dowers.

Partidas attributed to king Alfonso X, in the 13th century, only to be developed in the following centuries (Hespanha, 1993, pp. 964-965; Cardim, 2000, pp. 328-330). Such notions were also rooted in Christian representations, pervading kinship conceptions with spiritual connotations, thus entrenching the father-son relationship in an analogy with God and his son (Baschet, 2006, pp. 637-687; Perreux, 2023). Bartolomé Clavero's work on the evolution of legal thinking on primogeniture, based on the *ius divinum* and reworking concepts from the Roman period, such as the notion of representation between father and son, is fundamental in this regard (Clavero, 1986; 1992; 1993-1994). This dominant scheme coexisted alongside other variants adapted to each foundation's specific context. Such variants should motivate specific research to deepen our understanding of the founders who preferred succession by appointment of those deemed most suitable for the task, within the kinship structures¹²; and of others, even rarer, who preferred as their successors the youngest son¹³, family clerics¹⁴ (Soria Mesa, 2002; Irigoyen, 2004, pp. 129-130; Díaz, 2014, pp. 97-100), or women¹⁵ Spanish historiography has highlighted the

12. In 1690, Francisco da Rocha Tinoco, canon of the Cathedral of Braga, gave the administrators the power to choose a successor the descendant they considered most suitable to carry out the pious duties: *Will of Francisco da Rocha Tinoco*, 17 June 1690, Arquivo Distrital de Braga, Braga, Mitra Arquiepiscopal de Braga, Juízo dos Resíduos, lv. 14, Fols. 185-190.

13. In 1670, António Rodrigues and his wife Beatriz Domingues set up a entail in the parish of Vila Cova, in Barcelos, naming their great-niece Maria, and specifying that if she did not name a descendant as successor, it would be left to the youngest son or daughter: *Foundation deed by António Rodrigues and Beatriz Domingues*, 17 July 1670, Arquivo Distrital de Braga, Braga, Mitra Arquiepiscopal de Braga, Juízo dos Resíduos, lv. 746, Fols. 103v-105v.

14. In 1700, João Barreiros and his wife Maria Rodrigues declared that the entail should be passed on between relatives, appointing a priest or a person who could be ordained with their property's income: *Will of João Barreiros and Maria Rodrigues*, 18 June 1700, Arquivo Distrital de Portalegre, Portalegre, Provedoria da Comarca de Portalegre, box 16, Fols. 38-39v.

15. In 1630, Lopo Cabreira entailed the Sardos estate, leaving it to his daughter and specifying that women would be preferred in the succession: *Will of Lopo Cabreira*, 26 October 1630, Arquivo Distrital de Portalegre, Portalegre, Provedoria da Comarca de Portalegre, cx. 24, Fols. 49v-51. Although this subject requires further research, it appears that foundations favouring female succession were more common in densely entailed areas, such as the Atlantic islands and in the region of Portalegre, even though the scale of entail use in this last region might also be explained simply by the more systematic preservation of sources such as the records of the *Provedoria*. The *Provedorias da comarca* were a royal institution with regional representation charged with the surveillance of pious deeds. In theory, such competence required the preservation of information in their own records, thus instructing the founders or their heirs to register pious institutions (such as entails with obligations of masses) and present their wills or foundation deeds to be copied in the *Provedoria's* records. On the history of these institutions and their competence concerning entails related to specific patterns of information production and conservation, see: <https://visg.vinculum.fcsh.unl.pt/en/instituicoes/provedorias-das-comarcas-late-fifteenth-century-1832/>.

foundation of smaller entails to second-born children, although associated with a principal *mayorazgo* (Palencia Herrejón, 2002; Perez-García, 2009; Quintanilla Raso, 2006; Marzal Rodríguez 1996), a topic that requires further research in the Portuguese case. Overall, and despite the more regular schemes, the system, as it happened with every inheritance system, had some degree of flexibility (Ferrer-Alòs, 2007, pp. 44-47; 2014, pp. 36-37).

The variability of solutions, with their more and less salient aspects, reflects the founder's power to organise the lives of future generations. The common aspect is the definition of specific areas of kinship, which can be adapted to the specific context. Institutions were almost always projected onto the «linha direita», favouring vertical lines of descent, originating with the founders or first administrators, over collateral lines. The «linhas direitas» were, so to speak, the kinship hotspots. In turn, collateral lines were the support poles, the fields of operational kinship that were explored when the vertical lines of descent had been exhausted, expanding in variable ways to define the figure of the closest relative («parente mais chegado»). This admissible horizon for succession could coincide with the field of matrimonial interdicts, i.e., the 4th canonical degree¹⁶; or refer to relatives who shared the same name¹⁷; or extend to the 10th degree, basically admitting any tenuous relationship to find a successor¹⁸. In some cases, due to disagreements or rivalries¹⁹, but also without any specific justification, certain relatives and their lines of descent were excluded²⁰. Such limits inversely delineated cold spots within the parental universe, excluding relatives from the entail corporate body despite a genealogical proximity to the founders.

16. In 1640, António de Carvalho and Maria Antónia Carvalho set up an entail in Porto, clarifying that, in the absence of descendants, the last possessor could appoint as successor a relative up to the fourth degree that he considered suitable for the task: *Entail foundation deed by António de Carvalho and Maria Antónia de Carvalho*, 17 January 1640, TT, Lisbon, Arquivo do Arquivo, Livros de Registo, lv. 49, Fols. 355-358.

17. This is the case with the entail established by Maria Luís in 1487: when the outlined alternatives failed, she called her closest relative «from the Godinho lineage»: *Donation deed by Maria Luís*, 15 June 1487, TT, Lisbon, Feitos da Coroa, Capelas da Coroa, lv. 1, fl. 135v.

18. This is the case of the entail instituted in 1680 by Manuel Dias Maninho, a resident of Vale do Peso, in the town of Crato, which specified that if the lines of succession were exhausted, the entail would pass to the institutor's closest relative up to the 10th degree: *Will of Manuel Dias Maninho*, 10 March 1680, Arquivo Distrital de Portalegre, Portalegre, Provedoria da Comarca de Portalegre, box 12, Fols. 157v-161v.

19. In 1530, Mécia Dias, widow, chambermaid to Queen Leonor, explicitly excluded Isabel Antunes and her descendants because they disobeyed her father and her: *Will of Mécia Dias*, 9 September 1530, TT, Lisbon, Arquivo do Arquivo, Livros de Registo, lv. 52, Fols. 1v-3.

20. In 1422, Fernando Eanes Lobo excluded Lopo Fernandes, son of Pero Vivas, from the succession and every one of his generation: *Extract of Fernando Lopes Lobo's will*, 18 September 1422, TT, Lisbon, Feitos da Coroa, Núcleo Antigo 276, Fols. 101-102v. See also Rosa, 1995,

Between the admitted and rejected, those favoured and those sidelined, hot and cold spots within the parental universe were defined. These were primarily (but not exclusively) determined by consanguinity since such proximity was linked to ideals of similarity and unity: in fact, this was one of the theoretical bases for the conceptions forged in the medieval period about incest and marriage impediments (Guerreau-Jalabert, 2018). Verticality prevailed over horizontality, but the latter was used to mitigate generational randomness, especially prevalent in the *Ancien Régime*'s demographic system (Framiñán Santas and Garazo Presedo, 2005; Boone, 1986)²¹. In the more complete institutions, the founders (probably with the support of lawyers and other specialists) tried to foresee as many hypothetical scenarios as possible. The definition of hot and cold spots within the parental universe was formulated concentrically according to the blood ties with the founder. In the entail they established in 1560, Gil Eanes da Costa, a member of the king's council, and his wife Joana da Silva clearly outlined these preferential perimeters²². The first administrator would be the first-born son António, to be succeeded by his legitimate descendants, whereas illegitimate kin could only succeed in the absence of legitimate children. Only then were collateral relatives considered: first, Gil Eanes da Costa's relatives and secondly Joana da Silva's. In short, a contrast was designed and sometimes clearly stated between relatives and «strangers»²³, using different formulations and gradations.

What we have described is an operation of carving and pruning and defining hot and cold spots: the entail's potential heirs and successors did not coincide with the founder's universe of relatives, especially in a society whose foundational myth was that of a single original couple founding the whole of humanity (Hummers, 2018), and in which part of the nobility's self-representations, at least since the work of Pedro de Barcelos in the 14th century, were based on unity among multiple consanguineous ties as part of the world's *natural* order (Ferreira, 2020, pp. 191-216). Rather, the potential heirs were based on genealogical proximity and suitability for

21. Demography ceased to be a concern in many studies, but it is a fundamental backdrop to understand real social dynamics, along with some of the founders' concerns. The research of Framiñán Santas and Garazo Presedo on the nobility of Galicia clearly demonstrates the articulation between demographic constraints and the succession mechanisms, in a chronological context similar to that followed in this article. Although departing from somewhat uncertain data provided by genealogical literature, the observations made by James Boone on the Portuguese nobility in the late medieval-early modern period are also, in this regard, particularly relevant.

22. *Entail foundation deed by Gil Eanes da Costa and Joana da Silva*, 05 May 1560, TT, Lisbon, Morgados e capelas, Núcleo Antigo 190, Fols. 1-16.

23. In 1520, Afonso Eanes Vendeiro instituted a chapel in the church of Santa Maria do Bispo, in Montemor-o-Novo, declaring his intention that the entail should «always go to the closest relative of my generation, and not to strangers». *Will of Afonso Eanes Vendeiro*, 4 September 1520, TT, Lisbon, Arquivo do Arquivo, Livros de Registo, lv. 9, Fols. 276-278.

succession, starting with the descendants and always according to the founder's will. In any case, these definitions demonstrate the power of the founders as generational organisers through the entails they established.

3.2. *Regulating and constraining: shaping a corporate hierarchy of inequality*

The founders' power to carve and prune, moulding the kinship groups according to the entail, define them as pivotal figures. Such power organised the successive generations of administrators, creating hierarchies and defining roles, projecting the founders' memory, and prescribing behaviours for succeeding generations. In short, after carving and pruning, and in some cases becoming the true founder of a group emulating nobiliary ideals, the aim was to regulate and constrain behaviours. The combination of these two components moulded the kinship groups framed by entails.

We propose to analyse how entails regulated and constrained kinship groups by using a key idea: corporate hierarchy of inequality. There are several arguments in its favour, which highlight its analytical potential based on the historical specificity of the social formations in question. First, it allows us to distance ourselves from our conceptions of family relationships, which in principle frown upon unequal treatment, such as explicit favouritism in inheritances, a topic frequently emphasised by the groups who defended the abolition of entails throughout the 19th century (Esteves, 2008, pp. 60-61). The corporate hierarchy of inequality conceptualises inequality — based on gender and birth order — as a central point in the organisation of kinship groups and their insertion into the social contexts in which they were integrated (Johnson and Sabeau, 2011), allowing the attribution of different social roles to men and women, to first and second born children (Soria Mesa 2007, pp. 116-212; Cunha and Monteiro, 2010; Aguiar, 2021), and giving primacy to the *pater familias* within these social formations. This figure's power was also grounded on Christian representations and, despite its origin, had little in common with the overarching *dominium* it exercised in Roman society, including the power of life and death (Guerreau-Jalabert, 2007). In Spanish historiography, the work of Bartolomé Clavero and Juan Hernández Franco is particularly useful to understand the anthropological dimension of the *pater familias*, and the articulation between Roman and Christian thinking in its particular configuration during the early modern period (Clavero, 1993-94; Hernández Franco, 2007). We must also point out the importance of the work by Nicolas Perreaux on medieval representations on paternity (Perreaux, 2023), along with previous research on the subject (Baschet, 2000). Overall, in what concerns entails, the main idea was to have a figure of authority grounded on the

will of the founders, be them lay or ecclesiastical (Irigoyen, 2004; Díaz, 2014, 83)²⁴, and perpetually represented by the heir. The different roles and resulting authority relationships, although negotiable in each context and even if they were challenged (Rodríguez Pérez, 2012)²⁵, were somehow established in principle for the historical actors. As frequently sustained in Spanish historiography, entails reinforced the power of the *pater familias* or the *parente mayor*, and ultimately the importance of the «house» as a formation structuring the social fabric (Hernández Franco and Peñafiel Ramón, 1998; Molina Puche and Hernández Franco, 2010; Monteiro, 2001, 27-30). In this sense, the corporate hierarchy of inequality emphasises the naturalisation of such roles, hierarchies, rights, and duties that shaped the kinship relationships framed by entails or fideicommissum foundations in other regions of Europe (Chauvard, Bellavitis and Lanaro, 2012).

Portuguese historians sustained that the spread of entails since the late Middle Ages transformed the kinship organisation of aristocratic groups. The previous system was based on the equitable sharing of assets and subsequent pulverisation of the aristocracy's material basis (Sottomayor-Pizarro, 2013, 2016; Vasconcelos e Sousa, 2013). Recently, it has been argued that differentiated transmission mechanisms (inheritance and succession) coexisted between the 15th and 16th centuries. Based on differences between heirs and the diverse nature of the assets themselves, these mechanisms performed complementary social functions (Aguiar, 2021, 2022). Historiography on the 17th and 18th centuries conceded increasing weight to succession, suggesting the nobility was organised around an «entailment reproductive model» combined with the affirmation of a «house» organisation and other kinship practices, such as endogamy and consanguineous marriages (Monteiro, 2001; Cunha and Monteiro, 2010, pp. 50-66), probably especially pronounced in areas such as the Atlantic archipelagos (Rodrigues, 2002, 2013). In Spain, historians studying the family and nobility of the early modern period have defended the idea that entails progressively defined a primarily vertical kinship and a system based on «houses» (Hernández Franco and Peñafiel Ramón, 1998; Hernández Franco and Rodríguez Pérez, 2014; Dedieu, 1998; Soria Mesa, 2007, pp. 116-212). These groups

24. Some authors suggest interesting perspectives on the importance of ecclesiastical figures within kinship groups, amassing considerable wealth later rechannelled to nephews and nieces through the institution of entails. In this regard, they embodied the concept of the «ecclesiastical *pater familias*», as is suggested by Díaz. Along with this article, important insights on clerics as founders of entails are also offered by Irigoyen.

25. By studying the conflicts within the house of Vélez in the 16th century, Raimundo Rodríguez Pérez clearly demonstrates the tension between the juridical representation of the family as a peaceful body governed by the authority of the *pater familias*, and the real functioning of relationships within these formations. Inequality amongst heirs could thus pose serious challenges. As the author suggests, the study of conflicts allows the exploration of the inherent contradictions of these forms of social organization.

were well-defined around lines of succession and theoretically more circumscribed, formally framed by lineage chiefs who owned the most substantial and representative share of the estates. This concentration and the heir's respective benefits were formulated by the founders in terms of service to the founders and their souls, to relatives, to God and the kingdom. Through the idea of service, they sought to legitimise the subversion (or conditional acceptance) of the formal inequality between the legitimate heirs (Clavero, 1992, p. 230; Hespanha, 1993, pp. 964-967), sometimes attributing duties to the entail's successors towards their relatives.

This corporate hierarchy of inequality, an intrinsic part of how entails moulded kinship groups, occurred on two levels: a) when they were founded, by reserving the most substantial and representative parts of the inheritance for the entail and consequently its heir; b) by prescribing the relationship between heirs and their relatives: departing from an idealised and moralised image of this relationship, the heir assumed formal leadership based on a benefit-responsibility binomial wrapped up in Christian cultural representations. This dynamic progressively designed specific ways of organising kinship.

3.2.1. Concentrating the inheritance

Most institutions resorted to the «terça» (Abreu, 2001-2002, pp. 336-337), i.e., the abstract share of freely disposable property when there were forced heirs (i.e., legitimate descendants or ascendants). In other words, when there was more than one heir, the foundation of an entail presupposed one was favoured, but the others were not completely denied their rights to the paternal inheritance (Aguiar, 2021)²⁶. This dynamic can be observed diachronically in all the foundations. Such favouritism was expressed from the outset in the amount of assets: unless the founders expressly requested otherwise²⁷, the entail's heirs did not lose their right to the «legítima», that is, the share of the two thirds of the inheritance that was equally divided among the heirs. In addition, favouritism also reflected the quality of the assets, as the entail often included the most profitable or symbolic estates (Ferrer-Alôs, 2007, p. 54). Especially in socially rising groups, the lineage's name often derived from these symbolic estates the founders entailed, emulating the origins of the old aristocratic

26. As is suggested by this study, research on inheritance transmission — necessarily dependent on various types of documents (wills, partition deeds, marriage contracts) — demonstrates how, at least in the 15th and early 16th century, the coexistence of different mechanisms of concentration and sharing, namely through marriage dowries that sealed social pacts with other groups, was indispensable for the social cohesion of groups (Aguiar, 2022a).

27. In the entail instituted by Gonçalo Lourenço Gomide and his wife Inês Leitão, in 1398, the successor was urged not to share the rest of the inheritance with other children or grandchildren, since he was already favoured with the entail (Dias, 2005b: 77-80).

surnames, which usually had a territorial origin. In 1568, Diogo de Castro do Rio, from New Christian descent (Bethencourt, 2024, pp. 144-146), had an upward social trajectory connected to the overseas empire and became a *fidalgão da casa do rei*. Together with his wife Beatriz Vaz, he entailed the riverside estate they possessed in Sacavém, in the outskirts of Lisbon, which they understood to be the «manor of their nobility», and which would become the head of the entail²⁸. Sometimes these estates also bore the signs of the lineages, such as their coat-of-arms carved in stone (Rosa, 1995, pp. 109-110). A formulation such as the «manor of their nobility» was certainly inspired by the category of *nobreza de solar* (Pereira, 1998, pp. 305-315) and was part of the strategy of «honorific investment» (Olival, 2002)²⁹, converting economic capital into symbols of noble *status*, wherein entails played a decisive role. Gradually, the possession of entailed property, along with the crown's estates, became characteristic of noble and privileged groups (Monteiro, 2001; Aguiar, 2022a)³⁰.

Theoretically, founders without heirs had greater freedom when disposing of their assets, normally entailing all their estates once the testamentary legacies had been paid. When there was more than one heir and the founders entailed larger portions of the inheritance pertaining to the entail's presumptive heir or to his siblings, the affected parties had to formally renounce their inheritance, receiving in turn formally established compensations, such as lifetime annuities. The extensive process that led to the establishment of the entail of Taipa in 1538 is a good example. Maria da Silva entailed all her assets in Portugal and left the administration first to her son Nuno Álvares Pereira and then to her first-born son António Pereira and his descendants.

28. *Entail foundation deed by Diogo do Castro do Rio and Beatriz Vaz*, 19 May 1568, TT, Lisbon, Civil Government of Lisbon, 1st incorporation, Central Office/4th Office, Binding Register, NT 098, NP 0011, Fols. 143v-157.

29. The expression «investments in honour» comes from Fernanda Olival's article on four figures linked to commerce and royal institutions in the 16th century (including Diogo de Castro do Rio). These figures became wealthy, received letters of nobility and, among other investments, allocated part of their resources to purchase landed property. The foundation of entails favouring first-born sons, combined with matrimonial investments in daughters, was an integral part of their strategies.

30. Catarina de Sena Pereira, who instituted an entail in Lisbon in 1640, justified the foundation with «the desire to leave a memory of me to my descendants, and the usefulness that follows from having entailed estates in the houses of noble people» – *Will of Catarina de Sena Pereira*, 26 April 1630, TT, Lisbon, Arquivo do Arquivo, Livros de Registo, lv. 12, Fols. 41-43. In 1698, in Tarouca, João Teixeira de Araújo and Águeda de Sousa believed that entailing was «the most decorous way to perpetuate the nobility of their family, and to keep their memory alive in the minds of men»: *Entail foundation deed by João Teixeira de Araújo and Águeda de Sousa*, 21 November 1698, TT, Lisbon, Arquivo do Arquivo, Livros de Registo, lv. 3, Fols. 86v-91.

The incorporation of the portions belonging to the religious daughters implied their formal renunciations in exchange for payments and lifetime annuities³¹.

Royal confirmation of the foundation of entails was often requested to derogate inheritance laws (Rosa, 1995, pp. 240-244; Teixeira, 2003, pp. 1202-1205; Ayerbe Irribar, 2022, pp. 49-61). This strategy was used by law professionals or individuals connected to the royal circle with access to legal advice, thus guaranteeing the validity and perpetuity of the institution. This was the case, in 1378, of Afonso Domingues, a man connected to the royal officialdom. Arguing that entails were a favourable instrument for lineages and provided a good service to God and the kingdom, he and his wife asked the monarch to derogate the inheritance laws the entail contravened³², as it happened in other similar institutions (Rosa, 1995, pp. 240-244). In 1590, Álvaro de Sousa, a member of the king's council, and his wife Francisca de Távora entailed their reserved portions, appealing to their son and heir to add his share of the inheritance and compensate his siblings. Four years later, a royal letter of confirmation derogated the inheritance laws preventing the operations planned by the founders, thus validating the foundation³³. Unlike institutions constituted through wills (often composed at the end of the founders' lives), foundations that involved agreements between heirs and that presupposed collective understandings over a long period of time were established through specific foundation deeds³⁴. In a way, these documents revealed the foundation as a project involving all children, united around paternal authority and encompassed within an «anthropology of lineage». This concept was formalised by Atienza Hernández and is very useful for bringing together a set of elements that give meaning to the «family» as a specific institution in the early modern period: the importance of the founder, the *pater familias*, the moral economy of the house, the centrality of entails (Atienza Hernández, 1991).

Amidst these cases, between the 16th and 17th centuries, there was an enrichment of jurisprudence and treatises on entails, both in Portugal and Castille (Teixeira, 2003; Cabral, 2019), which laid the theoretical foundations for the subversion of the principle of equality between heirs, thus legitimising the corporate hierarchy of

31. The foundation deed, dated 1538-05-06, contains copies of eight documents relating to the assets and the transmission of the inheritance, setting out the agreements between the relatives: *Entail foundation deed by Maria da Silva*, 6 June 1538, TT, Lisbon, Morgados e Capelas, Registos Vinculares, Santarém, Processo 21, Fols. 66-83.

32. *Entail foundation deed by Afonso Domingues de Beja and Maria Domingues*, 9 September 1378, TT, Lisbon, Arquivo do Arquivo, Livro de Registo, lv. 16, Fols. 145-151.

33. *Entail foundation deed by Álvaro de Sousa and Francisca de Távora*, 8 November 1590, TT, Lisbon, Chancelaria de Filipe I, lv. 25, Fols. 143-146. The foundation deed is transcribed in the royal letter of confirmation derogating the laws, dated 1594-02-17.

34. For a characterisation of this documentary typology, as well other typologies involving entails, see: <https://visg.vinculum.fcsh.unl.pt/documentos/>.

inequality (Clavero, 1974, 125-130; Bermejo Castrillo, 2009, 565-572; Ayerbe Iribar, 2022, 49-62). This also implied that a conception of «distributive justice» superseded a strictly egalitarian distribution of the inheritance. Such notion was proposed by Juan Hernández Franco, who suggested tracing the historical evolution of the conceptions on inheritance, arguing that kinship groups aspired to this «distributive justice» rather than strictly egalitarian transmission practices to attain stability (Hernández Franco, 2011, p. 25). In Portugal, royal confirmation was primarily requested to derogate succession laws, allowing for a peaceful foundation process (Rosa, 1991, pp. 52-53). Furthermore, a conviction was also established that entails benefited the community, even if theoretically they harmed the interests of other heirs. With entails, the noble lineages and houses, essential bodies of the social fabric, were strengthened and thus made more suitable to serve God and the kingdom.

3.2.2. The heirs and their relatives: regulating and conditioning kinship relations

The founders believed that the creation of a stronger pole framed by the entail corporate body was a good solution for supporting relatives. This argument is found throughout the chronology, often in correlation with the advantages of entails in the service of God and the king. In the entail the bishop of Lisbon João Afonso de Brito instituted in 1329, he stressed that the foundation made it possible to «maintain an honourable estate» and, with it, to support relatives and serve the kings³⁵. In 1596, another bishop, Diogo Castilho, claimed the entail would ensure the existence of a wealthy relative (the owner of the entailed estates) whom relatives could resort to for support in difficult times³⁶. Support for relatives coexisted, however, with the control that could and should be exercised over them, forming a binary relationship based on various ideas. These included the pre-eminence of the *pater familias*, which formalised social leadership combined with Christian and charitable paternalism, in a form of authority that was both inherited/delegated and negotiated, but always based on duties filtered through *caritas* as a social ideal (Guerreau-Jalabert, 2000). Although specific, the figure of the «Parente mayor» is also useful for understanding the cultural grounds of such types of leaderships (Pereyra, 2015). Overall, these issues had a direct impact on the framework of family relations in the 16th and 17th centuries, shaping representations about the ownership of estates and specific family models filtered through a «corporate culture» (Cardim, 2000, pp. 205-246, 325-362). Such dimensions are simultaneously related to the idea of a corporate hierarchy

35. *Entail foundation deed by D. João Afonso de Brito*, 17 August 1329, TT, Lisbon, Casa de Abrantes, Order no. 67, 6E, doc. 1279.

36. *Donation deed by D. Pedro Castilho*, 18 April 1596, TT, Lisbon, Hospital de S. José, lv. 14, Fols. 15-25.

of inequality, with presupposed rights and duties in the relationships between the founders and their heirs, and between the heirs and their close relatives.

In foundations that entailed larger shares of the inheritance, the heirs were commonly required to provide lifetime annuities to their siblings. In 1520, Álvaro Cardoso obliged the first administrator to give a thousand gold *cruzados* for his sister's dowry³⁷. In 1650, João da Fonseca Coutinho and Maria Pereira de Vasconcelos ordered their first-born son and the entail's heir to support his brother Álvaro da Fonseca and his sisters, contributing to their convent dowries³⁸. Cases such as these were certainly intended to find balanced solutions, caring for the interests of the group embodied in the entail, while safeguarding the social fate and some material comfort for the other relatives, therefore fulfilling the institution's unitary ideal. At the same time, the fates of the other relatives could consolidate the parental group, through their insertion into secular and ecclesiastical spaces that were decisive in the social fabric.

For the same reasons, formal obligations were imposed upon future administrators, such as paying dowries to siblings and providing them with the material conditions to take their place in the world. In this case, there was no major concern over possible conflicts regarding inheritances; rather the entail's heir, due to his material and symbolic primacy, fully assumed a position of leadership that implied responsibilities, starting toward his siblings. This is what Fernando Fiel Lugo, who established a significant entail in Cape Verde in 1540, must have thought. Fernando made it a condition that the entail's successor support his brothers until they reached the age of 15 and his sisters until they married or professed in a convent, providing for their dowries. In fact, the amassing of dowries for sisters was one of the main reasons why entail administrators requested the liberation of entailed property, thus exposing the inherent tension between the integral maintenance of the institution and the fulfilment of familial duties, also essential to the kinship group's cohesion, a topic underlined by María Concepción Quintanilla Raso for Castilian *mayorazgos* (Quintanilla Raso, 2004, pp. 502-505) and also present in research on fideicommissum foundations in other parts of Europe (Cogné, 2012). Nevertheless, the administrator's authority and responsibility, as in the aforementioned foundation by Fernando Fiel Lugo, was not unbalanced: in this entail, the successor was also obliged to marry according to his parents' wishes³⁹. Similarly, in 1662, Manuel Malheiro and Isabel

37. *Entail foundation deed by Álvaro Cardoso*, 30 August 1520, TT, Lisbon, Feitos da Coroa, Núcleo Antigo 276, Fols. 51-53v.

38. *Will of João da Fonseca Coutinho and Maria Pereira de Vasconcelos*, 2 June 1650, AD Portalegre, Portalegre, Provedoria da Comarca de Portalegre, Tombos de capelas e morgados, lv. 11, Fols. 129v-131v.

39. *Entail foundation deed by Fernando Fiel Lugo*, 23-25 June 1540, TT, Lisbon, Chancelaria de D. João III, lv. 40, Fols. 169-170v.

Fernandes stipulated that when the entail's administrators had more than one child, the administrator was obliged to support the second-born academic studies at the University of Coimbra for ten years⁴⁰. In 1590, the institutor Manuel Colaço, a judge at the high court of *Casa da Suplicação*, recommended that the first-born and heir use his entail's income to help «guide and support his brothers and sisters»⁴¹. These obligations were not always explicitly formulated by the founders, but they were underpinned by centuries of discussions led by jurists and treatise writers on the legitimacy of entails, and by the theoretical inversion of inheritance rights they implied, formulating concepts such as the «direito de alimentos» (Clavero, 1974, pp. 262-232; 1992, pp. 228-230; Marzal Rodríguez, 1996, pp. 306-317; Monteiro, 2001, pp. 29-30; Melero Muñoz, 2021, pp. 75-76, 110-116, 162-1659); or by the aforementioned principle of exemption from inheritance laws because entails benefited the kingdom (Hespanha, 1993, pp. 964-966).

The power given to administrators came with obligations towards relatives, lineage, God and the king. It was based on a relational binomial between founders and successors, with duties and obligations, whereby the former outlined certain physical and moral profiles for the heirs, through clauses and discursive pieces (Rosa, 1988). The obligation to marry with the agreement of relatives — and implicitly an honourable and profitable marriage for the lineage — was sometimes formulated⁴², thus constraining the future profile of the relatives framed by the entail. Here, too, we can find ways to excluded unwanted relatives from the succession. In the institution João Martins Ferreira established in Porto, in 1492, he stipulated that successors should never marry their Ferreira relatives from Casal de Cavaleiros, because of the grievances against his father. Furthermore, if the entail was possessed by a woman, she was obliged to marry in the city⁴³. This last example emphasises how matrimonial control became even more common when there was a female successor: she was expected to marry a man with the necessary qualities to administer the entail⁴⁴. In

40. *Will of Manuel Malheiro*, 19 May 1662, TT, Lisbon, Hospital de S. José, lv. 20, Fols. 62-77v.

41. *Will of Manuel Colaço*, 05 January 1590, TT, Lisbon, Morgados e Capelas, Vínculos, Coimbra, no. 10, Fols. 10-22v.

42. The social status of the spouse sometimes served to mitigate this clause, making it non-absolute. For example, Gil Eanes da Costa and Joana da Silva, in the entail they established in 1560, stipulated that the heirs were obliged to marry according to their parents or grandparents' wishes, unless the women was a «noble daughter of noble parents and grandparents by blood»: *Entail foundation deed by Gil Eanes da Costa and Joana da Silva*, 05 May 1560, TT, Lisbon, Morgados e capelas, Núcleo Antigo 190, Fols. 1-16.

43. *Entail foundation deed by João Martins Ferreira*, 10 September 1492, ADP, Porto, Provedoria da Comarca do Porto, K/21/2-43, Fols. 13-19.

44. In the will establishing his entail in 1560, which included the chapel his father had founded in Chaves, Francisco Rodrigues stipulated that, in the event of female succession, the

this scenario there was also often the obligation to pass on the surname or coat of arms of the founders, in an attempt to ensure that their symbols were not diluted by those of the heiress' husband.

Since the 16th century, alongside the incorporation of blood purity laws into the kingdom's legal system⁴⁵, clauses began to appear preventing marriages with people from the «Hebrew nation». This was in addition to the exclusions of Moors and mulattos, following an increasingly established ethnic-racial logic (Bethencourt, 2021). These marriages were excluded to avoid «suffering such serious blemishes in a family and succession that [the founder] wishes to be perpetual, noble, pure and Christian», as judge Francisco Mendes Pimentel stated in his institution in 1690⁴⁶. The religious and ethnic-racial dimension was one manifestation of an increasingly formally stratified society (Pereira, 1998, pp. 334-335). In a 1620 institution founded by Manuel da Silveira Frade, *cavaleiro da casa do rei*, an extensive list of forbidden conditions for the marriages of the entail's successors was articulated: not only were those who married against their parents' wishes excluded, but also those who married people of an «infected race» and those who married «the son of a peon or a mechanical officer»⁴⁷. The entail founders affirmed the nobiliary logic they sought when using this legal resource by imposing marriage clauses upon the presumptive heirs.

4. DIACHRONIC PERSPECTIVES

At this point, we can formulate a series of far-reaching questions. To what extent were the founders able to effectively constrain and shape kinship groups and individual behaviour, starting with the successors of the entails? Did entails succeed in producing unity and stability over the long term, as desired and expressed by certain founders? Were kinship structures shaped by a framework specific to entails? Was the development of entails part of an overall process, characterised by certain authors, tending towards the progressive affirmation in Europe, between the Middle Ages and the early modern period, of «more institutionalised forms of organising power»

woman should marry «a person with the qualities those who succeed in this administration should have». *Will of Francisco Rodrigues*, 16 October 1560, TT, Lisbon, Arquivo do Arquivo, Livro de Registo, lv. 43, Fols. 89v-92.

45. On Iberian societies, blood was a metaphorical substance, also rooted in Christian images, but with a very complex evolution. On this issue, see: Guerrau-Jalabert, 2013. Delille, 2013. Ruiz, 2015.

46. *Entail foundation deed by Francisco Mendes Pimentel*, 22 February 1690, TT, Lisbon, Arquivo do Arquivo, Livro de Registo, lv. 39, Fols. 112v-118v.

47. *Entail foundation deed by Manuel da Silveira Frade and Martinho da Silveira Frade*, 19 December 1620, TT, Lisbon, Morgados e capelas, Núcleo Antigo 193.

intrinsically related to more defined schemes of kinship structures and relationships (Sabeian and Teuscher, 2007)⁴⁸? Based on these questions and this article's description, the overall hypothesis is that the diffusion and intensification of entail foundations generated a kinship framework that, as we have tried to demonstrate, combined ways of carving and pruning descent groups within the broader horizontal kinship structures. A form of organisation combining elements of theological, legal and nobiliary thought, based on the power of the founder, who defined the «internal laws» of the entails, its own rules and corporate nature, through the institutional framework and clauses contained in the founding documents.

To answer these questions and test the hypotheses and conceptualisation constructed to understand the phenomenon over the long term, it is necessary to use a wider and more diverse set of sources. By mobilising documentation of different types one can, on the one hand, investigate the organisation of kinship groups and, on the other hand, reconstruct the history of entails, thus constructing integrated visions. To finalise this article, we provide some examples to demonstrate possible research pathways. Judicial documentation, especially abundant since the 17th century, provides many elements to consider different problems (Lagunas, 2007; Melero Muñoz, 2021). The provenance of such documentation is nowadays divided into two repositories. One is the result of work by Manuel Álvares Pegas, a 17th-century jurist who, in his five-volume treatise on entails⁴⁹, sought to collect the law in force, as well as opinions and court decisions that provide material to characterise this legal institute (Teixeira, 2003). The other repository results from the activity of the *Comissão and Juízo das Capelas da Coroa*⁵⁰.

One of the points raised above regarding the regulation of kinship through the founding documents was the marriage of the heirs. How were these conditions received? And what effects did they have on the articulation of kinship groups? In 1671, Manuel Correia de Lacerda accused Luísa Maria Antónia de Portugal — daughter of Luís de Sá e Meneses and the last administrator of the entail established by Carlos

48. A reflection proposed by Sabeian and Teuscher, 2007, in their collective book on the evolution of the European kinship system between 1300 and 1900.

49. *Tractatus de exclusione, inclusione, successione, & erectione maioratus*, 1685-1739.

50. Throughout several phases at least since 1574, the crown tried to record its entails, along with their assets, income, and pious charges. In 1604-1605, a commission for the *Capelas da Coroa* was set up within the *Casa da Suplicação* — a court responsible for appeals in civil and criminal cases since the 15th century. Until the 1640s, there were hundreds of chapels whose right of administration belonged to the crown, which often ceded this right to third parties. For a characterisation of these institutions, see the sheets produced as part of the *Vinculum Information System Guide*: <https://visg.vinculum.fcsh.unl.pt/instituicoes/comissao-do-tombodas-capelas-da-coroa/>; <https://visg.vinculum.fcsh.unl.pt/instituicoes/juizo-das-capelas-da-coroa-1643-1832/>.

Nunes — of not being entitled to the administration⁵¹. Among other arguments, he claimed that she had married without her father's permission, in direct violation of one of the institution's clauses. The defendant recognised the existence of this clause, designed to prevent marriages «with people of unequal quality». However, she argued that she had married a man of «quality and nobility» and that her father had approved the marriage, receiving the couple in his house, supporting them and being godfather to their first child. Luísa was thus judged to be the rightful owner of the entail. In another case, in 1673, Diogo de Barros de Azevedo, as guardian of his son Manuel de Figueiredo de Lacerda, argued that Manuel de Figueiredo de Lacerda and Pedro Barbosa de Figueiredo had founded an entail defining that the successors «would not marry people who were of Jewish race or from another infected nation, or people of a much lower quality»⁵². However, Pedro Barbosa de Figueiredo, who became the first administrator, had married Isabel de Almeida, who was accused of low social status and improper sexual behaviour. These conditions led the court to dispossess him of the entail.

These two cases highlight how conflicts were resolved based on the founder's will. Disputants and decision-makers referred to this institutional document, whose authority is fully justified if we remember the founder's will was the entail's «internal law»⁵³. The cases also show a notorious vigilance among relatives. Within the sphere of potential successors, and even more so within the kinship hotspots, strict vigilance was exercised, placing the administrators under the scrutiny of their relatives.

Conflicts between relatives regarding succession rights were apparently more common. In these cases, the disputants tried to prove their genealogical connections, which were sometimes quite deep in time. This was the case, for example, with the succession dispute, between 1691 and 1692, over the ownership of the entail established by Gil do Sem and Branca Eanes in the early 15th century. In 1691, the entail was judged to be vacant for the Crown because the Count of Sarzedas, who claimed possession, had not duly proved his kinship ties to the institutors⁵⁴. In the following year, however, a new judgement considered him to be the entail's legitimate administrator⁵⁵, when it was finally proved he was a descendant of Grimaneza Mascarenhas, daughter of Pedro do Sem and descendant of the institutor. The proofs

51. The sentence, dated 11 June 1671, is transcribed in Manuel Álvares Pegas, *Tractatus de exclusione, inclusione, successione, & erectione maioratus*, 1687, vol. 2, 583-584.

52. The sentence, dated 7 September 1673, is transcribed in Manuel Álvares Pegas, *Tractatus de exclusione, inclusione, successione, & erectione maioratus*, 1685, vol. 1, 595

53. Rosa, 1995, 221-222.

54. *Acórdão*, 28 July 1691, TT, Lisbon, Arquivo do Arquivo, Livros de Registo, lv. 2, Fols. 177v-181.

55. *Acórdão*, 20 August 1692, TT, Lisbon, Arquivo do Arquivo, Books of Records, lv. 2, Fols. 181-182v.

were certificates taken from genealogical books, whose information was compatible with other documents consulted in the archives of the *Mesa da Consciência* and the *Torre do Tombo*.

In this case, the basis of the claim and the victory in the dispute was based on genealogical arguments. In these last three examples, there was vigilance between relatives and a deep and apparently justified knowledge of generational and kinship connections (Soria Mesa, 2004). Maria de Lurdes Rosa stresses that the production of genealogical knowledge was central for legal purposes, which explains why such documents were included in family archives, wherein entails often formed the organisational backbone (Nóvoa and Rosa, 2018, pp. 8-9). Rosa argues that entails, along with blood purity issues, were the great catalysts for genealogical production throughout the early modern period (Rosa, 2019)⁵⁶. Entails reinforced the indispensability of genealogical knowledge, already necessary in the context of matrimonial impediments (Rosa, 1998; Aguiar, 2022b)⁵⁷ and central to the nobility's identity, grounded on medieval genealogical books.

Growing social stratification and endogamy within power groups may have favoured increased vigilance and conflicts. The hypothesis suggested by Soria Mesa — according to which entails with regular succession schemes (i.e., male preference, but with the possibility of female succession as an alternative) favoured the concentration of entails in the same groups over the long term — may also help clarify these dynamics (Soria Mesa, 2007, pp. 226-227). The concentration of entails was made possible and reinforced by genealogical knowledge, superimposed on a broader set of social transformations. This occurred as the number of new foundations constantly increased, extending to more social groups, thus making it theoretically possible for a greater number of kinship groups to live under the framework of entails. These were perhaps more visible and more constraining in the groups that accumulated the administration of several institutions. Overall, authors such as Manuel Pérez García suggest that, in the long run, entails progressively constrained kinship structures, undermining their cohesion and socially reproductive capacity. The growing frequency of succession conflicts, the endogamous concerns, and the matrimonial restriction eventually reduced the amplitude of the groups' relations (Pérez-García, 2009, 2021). By the end of the *Ancien Régime*, families faced ruin, and the system was under attack by the new bourgeois elites (Monteiro, 2012, pp. 139-177). Entails were a constitutive element of the old social order, and their

56. On genealogical knowledge and questions of blood purity, see Figueirôa-Rego, 2008.

57. In the context of consanguinity, these required dispensations up to the 4th canonical degree and consequently genealogical knowledge up to the third generation. The research carried out by Maria de Lurdes Rosa at the Vatican archives clearly demonstrated the knowledge on this subject by Portuguese elites at the end of the Middle Ages.

specific form of organizing kinship was regarded by the new dominant groups as inconceivable and irrational, although they were defended or later appropriated by conservative groups, such as those connected to *Integralismo Lusitano* (Rosa, 1995, pp. 28-31; Esteves, 2009, pp. 28-113). In some regions of Spain, however, the disappearance of entails and the affirmation of new elites came with different solutions to produce the same effects, perpetuating forms of inheritance that continued to favour the concentration of estates in one line (Sáinz de Rozas, 1991). The aforementioned research carried out by J. Esteves also studies how the old elites of the region of Castelo Branco, in Portugal, adapted to the disappearance of entails, demonstrating the solutions adopted by the groups (Esteves, 2009, pp. 144-293). However different and implausible in the new social order, entails and their ways of organising social dynamics had its own rationale: historians need to overcome the layers of criticism on entails and *Ancien Régime* structures by their 18th-19th centuries detractors, frequently associating the *Ancien Régime*'s institutional landscape within the perception of the «underdeveloped» Southern European societies (Yun-Casalilla, 1998). To construct a coherent vision of the past, historians must build a specific theoretical framework, as it was intended in this article.

The vast set of questions raised above can only be fully answered with further research. Nevertheless, one can surmise that the evolution of entails and their enormous diffusion clearly conditioned kinship structures. They contributed to a greater definition of groups, formalising their structures more clearly, determining hot and cold spots primarily by blood proximity to the institutor and/or the entail's heirs. They also defined, in a more formal way, the relationships between relatives within the corporate body, establishing a corporate hierarchy of inequality that was the basis, and at the same time the reinforcing condition, of the power of the group's head or chief, the *pater familias* and central element in the chain of inter-generational relationships. However, as the abundance of judicial documentation demonstrates, especially since the 17th century, the existence of entails was not peaceful. Despite the longevity of these institutions and the unifying intentions proclaimed by some of their founders, conflicts over succession and other issues have multiplied, highlighting the distances (which are always worth questioning) between the representations behind the actions of historical actors and the actual unfolding of social dynamics. However, the fact that conflicts arose and were resolved within a framework that was recognised as effective and inescapable in its immanent characteristics, demonstrates how this institution became deeply entrenched and relevant in shaping social relations, starting with kinship as a fundamental structure in medieval and early modern Portuguese society.

Authorship and contribution policy

Miguel Aguiar declares that he is the sole author of this article. He has independently performed all tasks related to the research, analysis, writing, and revision of the text. He also assumes full responsibility for the content presented here.

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Statement on the use of artificial intelligence

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5. BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abreu, L. (2001-2002). Algumas considerações sobre vínculos. *Revista Portuguesa de História*, XXXV, 335-346.
- Aguiar, M. (2021). *Aristocracia, parentesco e reprodução social em Portugal no final da Idade Média* (unpublished PhD thesis). Universidade do Porto, Université Paris 1 Panthéon-Sorbonne, Portugal, France. Recovered from <https://repositorio-aberto.up.pt/handle/10216/135875>.
- Aguiar, M. (2022a). Sucessão e herança: transmissão e reprodução social da aristocracia portuguesa no final da Idade Média. *Cuadernos de Estudios Gallegos*, 69 (135). <https://doi.org/10.3989/ceg.2022.135.07>.
- Aguiar, M. (2022b). Why Marriage Mattered? Marriage and Social Reproduction - the Case of Late Medieval Portuguese Aristocracy (1380-1530). *Edad Media. Revista de Historia*, 23. <https://doi.org/10.24197/em.23.2022.153-185>.
- Anheim, É. (2012). L'historien au pays des merveilles? Histoire et anthropologie au début du XXI^e siècle. *L'Homme*, 203-204, 399-427.
- Atienza Hernández, I. (1991). Teoría y administración de la casa, linaje, familia extensa, ciclo vital y aristocracia en Castilla (s. XVI-XIX). In F. Chacón Jiménez (coord.), *Familia, grupos sociales y mujer en España (s. XV-XIX)* (p. 13-48). Murcia: Universidad de Murcia.
- Ayerbe Irribar, M. R. (2022). Notas sobre la sucesión y el mayorazgo en Castilla y en los territorios vascos. In I. Ruiz Rodríguez and F. Martínez Llorente (coord.), *La Historia e el Derecho de España: Visiones y Pareceres* (p. 49-77). Madrid: Dykinson.
- Barry, L. et al (2000). Glossaire. *L'Homme. Revue française d'anthropologie*, 154-155. <https://doi.org/10.4000/lhomme.58>.

- Baschet, J. (2000). *Le sein du père. Abraham et la paternité dans l'Occident médiéval*. Paris: Gallimard.
- Baschet, J. (2006). *La civilisation féodale. De l'an mil à la colonisation de l'Amérique*. Paris: Flammarion.
- Bermejo Castrillo, M. A. (2009). *Entre ordenamientos y códigos. Legislación y doctrina sobre familia a partir de las leyes de Toro*. Madrid: Dykinson.
- Bethencourt, F. (2021). Managing Diversity in the Portuguese Empire. *E-Journal of Portuguese History*, 19 (2). <https://doi.org/10.26300/px7m-4439>.
- Bethencourt, F. (2024). *Strangers Within. The Rise and Fall of the New Christian Trading Elite*. Princeton | Oxford: Princeton University Press.
- Boone, J. L. (1986). Parental Investment and Elite Family Structure in Preindustrial States: a case study of Late Medieval-Early Modern Portuguese Genealogies. *American Anthropologist*, 88 (4), 859-878.
- Brito, P. (1997). *Patriciado Urbano Quinhentista: as famílias dominantes do Porto (1500-1580)*. Porto: Arquivo Histórico / Câmara Municipal do Porto.
- Cabral, G. (2019). Foreign Law and Circulation of Ideas in the Early Modern Age: Analyzing an 'allegatio' of Manuel Álvares Pegas on *maioratus*. *Forum historiae iuris* 03-04. Recovered from <https://forhistiur.net/2018-12-cabral/abstract/?l=en>.
- Cardim, P. (2000). *O Poder dos Afectos. Ordem amorosa e dinâmica política no Portugal do Antigo Regime* (unpublished PhD thesis). Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal.
- Chauvard, J-F; Bellavitis, A.; Lanaro, P. (2012). De l'usage du fidéicommiss à l'âge moderne. État des lieux. *Mélanges de l'École française de Rome - Italie et Méditerranée modernes et contemporaines*, 124 (2). <https://doi.org/10.4000/mefrim.650>.
- Clarvero, B. (1974). *Mayorazgo. Propiedad feudal en Castilla (1369-1836)*. Madrid: Siglo XXI de España Editores.
- Clavero, B. (1986). *De maioratus nativitate et nobilitate concertatio*. *Anuario de historia del derecho español*, 56, 921-929.
- Clavero, B. (1992). *Favor Maioratus, Usus Hispaniae: Moralidad de Linaje entre Castilla y Europa*. In L. Bonfield (ed.), *Marriage, Property, and Succession* (p. 215-254). Berlin: Duncker and Humblot.
- Clavero, B. (1993-1994). *Beati dictum: derecho de linaje, economía de familia y cultura de orden*. *Anuario de Historia del derecho español*, 63-64, 7-148.
- Cogné, A. (2012). Le fidéicommiss, un instrument d'immobilisation des patrimoines? Le cas de la Lombardie durant la période moderne. *Mélanges de l'École française de Rome - Italie et Méditerranée modernes et contemporaines*, 124 (2). <https://doi.org/10.4000/mefrim.925>.
- Cunha, M S., & Monteiro, N. G. (2010). Aristocracia, Poder e Família em Portugal, Séculos XV-XVIII. In M. S. Cunha & J. Hernández Franco (org.) *Sociedade, Família e Poder na Península Ibérica: elementos para uma História Comparada / Sociedad, Familia y Poder en la Península Ibérica: elementos para una Historia Comparada* (p. 47-75). Lisboa: Colibri/ CIDEHUS - Universidade de Évora - Universidad de Murcia.

- Dedieu, J. P. (1998). Familles, majorats, réseaux de pouvoir. Estrémadure, XV^e-XVIII^e siècle. In J. P. Dedieu & J. L. Castellano (dir.) *Réseaux, familles et pouvoirs dans le monde Ibérique à la fin de l'Ancien Régime*, (p. 111-145). Paris : CNRS Éditions.
- Delille, G. (2013). The Shed Blood of Christ: From Blood as Metaphor to Blood as Bearer of Identity. In C. Johson, B. Jussen, D. Warren Sabeau & S. Teuscher (eds.) *Blood & Kinship. Matter for Metaphor from Ancient Rome to the Present* (p. 125-143). New York / Oxford: Berghahn
- Dias, J. (2005a). *Chancelarias Portuguesas. D. João I. Volume II, tomo I (1385-1392)*. Lisboa: Centro de Estudos Históricos – Universidade Nova de Lisboa.
- Dias, J. (2005b). *Chancelarias Portuguesas. D. João I. Volume II, tomo I (1391-1407)*. Lisboa: Centro de Estudos Históricos – Universidade Nova de Lisboa.
- Díaz, A. J. (2014). Élités eclesiásticas locales y financiación de estrategias familiares: los prebendados de la catedral de Córdoba en época moderna. In R. Molina Recio (dir.) *Familia y economía en los territorios de la Monarquía Hispánica (ss. XVI-XVIII)* (p. 73-115). Badajoz: Mandalay.
- Esteves, J. (2008). *Do Morgadio à divisão igualitária dos bens. Extinção do morgadio e estratégias de perpetuação do poder familiar (entre o fim do século XIX e o século XX)* (unpublished PhD thesis). Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Portugal.
- Ferrer-Alôis, L. (2007). Comment se perpétuer? Systèmes successoraux et transmission patrimoniale dans l'Espagne du XVIII^e siècle. *Histoire et Sociétés Rurales*, 27, 37-70.
- Ferrer-Alôis, L. (2014). ¿Quién hereda? Desigualdades de género en el acceso a los derechos de propiedad y sistemas hereditarios en España. *Areas. Revista Internacional de Ciencias Sociales*, 33, 35-47.
- Ferreira, M. R. (2020). *Pedro de Barcelos e a escrita da História*. Porto: Estratégias Criativas.
- Figureirôa-Rego, J. (2008). Family genealogical records: cleansing and social reception (Portugal – 16th to 18th century). *E-Journal of Portuguese History*, 6 (1). Recovered from https://www.brown.edu/Departments/Portuguese_Brazilian_Studies/ejph/html/issue11/html/jrego.html.
- Framiñán Santas, A. M., & Garazo Presedo, A. (2005). Estructuras de parentesco de la nobleza gallega en 1350-1600. *Obradoiro de Historia Moderna*, 14, 109-140.
- Guerreau-Jalabert, A. (2000). *Caritas* y Don en la Sociedad Medieval Occidental. *Hispania*, 60 (24), 27-62.
- Guerreau-Jalabert, A. (2007). Rome et l'Occident Médiéval: quelques propositions pour une analyse comparée de deux sociétés à système de parenté complexe. In J-P. Genet (coord.) *Rome et l'État Moderne Européen* (p. 197-216). Rome: École Française de Rome.
- Guerreau-Jalabert, A. (2013). Flesh and blood in Medieval Language about Kinship. In C. Johson, B. Jussen, D. Warren Sabeau & S. Teuscher (eds.), *Blood & Kinship. Matter for Metaphor from Ancient Rome to the Present* (p. 61-82). New York / Oxford: Berghahn Books.
- Guerreau-Jalabert, A. (2018). L'apport des données médiévales à l'analyse du système d'alliance européen. *L'Atelier du Centre de recherches historiques*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.4000/acrh.8619>.

- Haddad, É. (2012). Les substitutions fidéicommissaires dans la France d'Ancien Régime : droit et historiographie. *Mélanges de l'Ecole Française de Rome. Italie et Méditerranée modernes et contemporaines*, 124 (2). <https://doi.org/10.4000/mefrim.690>.
- Herculano, A. (1983). *Opúsculos*, tomo II, *Questões Públicas, Sociedade, Economia, Direito*. Lisboa: Livraria Bertrand.
- Hernández Franco, J., & Peñafiel Ramón, A. (1998). Parentesco, linaje y mayorazgo en una ciudad mediterránea: Murcia (siglos XV-XVIII). *Hispania*, 58 (198), 157-183.
- Hernández Franco, J., & Rodríguez Pérez, R. A. (2014). Formación y desarrollo de las casas nobiliarias castellanas (siglos XVI-XVII). In J. Hernández Franco, J. A. Guillén Berrendero & S. Martínez Hernández (eds.), *Nobilitas: estudios sobre la nobleza y lo nobiliario en la Europa moderna* (p. 139-175). Madrid: Ediciones Doce Calles.
- Hernández Franco, J. (2007). Reflexiones sobre la figura del padre en la edad moderna. In J. Vilar Ramírez, A. Peñafiel Ramón & A. Irigoyen López (coord.), *Historia y sociabilidad: homenaje a la profesora María del Carmen Melendreras Gimeno* (p. 231-244). Murcia: Universidad de Murcia.
- Hernández Franco, J. (2011). Historiar e historizar la herencia. *Studia historica: Historia moderna*, 33, 17-28.
- Hespanha, A. M. (1993). Carne de uma só carne: para uma compreensão dos fundamentos histórico-antropológicos da família na época moderna. *Análise Social*, 28 (123-124), 951-973.
- Hummers, H. (2018). *Visions of Kinship in Medieval Europe*. Oxford University Press.
- Irigoyen, A. (2004). La Iglesia y la perpetuación de las familias: clero y mayorazgo en Castilla durante el Antiguo Régimen. In M. Ghirardi (org.), *Familias iberoamericanas ayer y hoy. Una mirada interdisciplinaria, Programa de Estructuras y Estrategias familiares* (p. 113-133). Centro de Estudios Avanzados, Universidad Nacional de Córdoba, ALAP Editor.
- Johson, C., & Sabeen, D. W. (2011). From Siblingship to Siblinghood: Kinship and the Shaping of European Society (1300-1900). In C. H. Johnson & D. W. Sabeen (eds.), *Sibling Relations and the Transformations of European Kinship, 1300-1900* (p. 1-30). New York / Oxford: Berghahn Books.
- Kuchenbuch, L. (2004). Sources ou documents? Contribution à l'histoire d'une évidente méthodologique. *Hypothèses*, 7, 287-315.
- Lagunas, C. (2007). Mayorazgos de mujeres. Conflictos por la sucesión en las herencias de bienes familiares vinculados. In *XI Jornadas Interescuelas/Departamentos de Historia. Departamento de Historia. Facultad de Filosofía y Letras. Universidad de Tucumán, San Miguel de Tucumán*. San Miguel de Tucumán: Universidad de Tucumán. Recovered from <https://cdsa.aacademica.org/000-108/110>.
- Lemeunier, G. (1993). «Porque las cosas divididas sin memoria perecen». Regard anthropologique sur le majorat castillan. In *La vie, la mort, la foi, le temps. Mélanges offerts à Pierre Chaunu* (p. 719-723). Paris: PUF.
- Marzal Rodríguez, P. (1996). Una visión jurídica de los mayorazgos valencianos entre la época foral y la nueva planta. *Anuario de historia del derecho español*, 66, 229-364.

- Melero Muñoz, I. M. (2019). Mujeres y vinculaciones de bienes: el androcentrismo y el discurso legitimador en los pleitos de mayorazgo. In M. A. Fernández Valle, C. López Calderón & I. Rodríguez Moya (eds.), *Discursos e imágenes del barroco iberoamericano* (vol. 8, p. 329-344). Santiago de Compostela/Sevilla: Andavira, EnredARS.
- Melero Muñoz, I. M. (2021). *Linaje, vinculación de bienes y conflictividad en las elites nobiliarias de la España moderna. Los conflictos en torno a la sucesión del mayorazgo (XVII-XVIII)* (Unpublished PhD thesis): Universidad de Sevilla, Spain.
- Molénat, J.-P. (1986). La volonté de durer: majorats et chapellenies dans la pratique tolédane des XIII^e-XV^e siècles. *En la España medieval*, 9, 683-696.
- Molina Puche, S., & Hernández Franco, J. (2010). Aristocracia, familia-linaje, mayorazgo. La casa de los marqueses de Villena en la edad moderna. *Historia social*, 66, 3-22.
- Monteiro, N. G. (2001). Trajectórias sociais e formas familiares: o modelo de sucessão vincular. In F. Chácon Jiménez and J. Hernández Franco (eds.), *Familias, poderosos y oligarquias* (p.17-37). Murcia: Universidad de Murcia.
- Monteiro, N. G. (2012). *Elites e poder. Entre o Antigo Regime e o Liberalismo*. Lisboa: Imprensa de Ciências Sociais.
- Morsel, J. (2000). Ce qu'écrire veut dire au Moyen Âge. Observations préliminaires à une étude de la scripturalité médiévale. *Memini. Travaux et documents de la Société des études médiévales du Québec*, 4, 3-43.
- Morsel, J. (2004a). Le médiéviste, le lignage et l'effet de réel. La construction du *Geschlecht* par l'archive en Haute-Allemagne à partir de la fin du Moyen Âge. *Revue de Synthèse*, 125, 83-110.
- Morsel, J. (2004b). Les sources sont-elles le «pain de l'historien»? *Hypothèses*, 7, 271-286.
- Morsel, J. (2017). *Noblesse, parenté et reproduction sociale à la fin du Moyen Âge*. Paris: Picard
- Nóvoa, R. S., & Rosa, M. L. (2018). The Study of Ancien Régime Family Archives in Portugal: research pathways and themes. *Revista Brasileira de História*, 38 (78), 2-20.
- Olival, F. (2002). Juristas e mercadores à conquista das honras: quatro processos de nobilitação quinhentistas. *Revista de História Econômica e Social*, 4, 7-53.
- Palencia Herrejón, J. R. (2002). Estrategia patrimonial y jerarquía del linaje: los mayorazgos de la Casa Ducal de Maqueda en el siglo XVI. *Historia. Instituciones. Documentos*, 29, 337-356.
- Pereira, J. C. (1998). A estrutura social e o seu devir. In J. Dias (coord.), *Portugal: do renascimento à crise dinástica* (p. 277-336). Lisboa: Editorial Presença.
- Pereyra, O. V. (2015). «Como casas sin çimiento...». Dinámica parental y articulación territorial en los espacios septentrionales del reino de Castilla en la tardo Edad Media y la temprana modernidad. *Magallanica: revista de historia moderna*, 3, 144-185.
- Pérez García, M. (2009). Entre la Corona de Castilla y la de Aragón: el mayorazgo y la propiedad vinculada entre el Reino de Murcia y el de Valencia (ss. XVII-XVIII). In S. Molina Puche & A. Irigoyen López (coord.), *Territorios distantes, comportamientos similares. Familias, redes y reproducción social en la Monarquía Hispánica (siglos XIV-XIX)* (p. 345-372). Murcia: Universidad de Murcia, Servicio de Publicaciones.

- Pérez García, M. (2021). *Blood, land and power: the rise and fall of the Spanish nobility and lineages in the early modern period*. Cardiff: University of Wales Press.
- Perreaux, N. (2023). «*In nomine patris...* Éléments pour une sémantique de la paternité médiévale». In L. Dumont, O. Julien & S. Lamassé (dir.), *Histoire de mots. Saisir le passé grâce aux données textuelles*. Éditions de la Sorbonne: Paris. Recovered from <https://shs.hal.science/halshs-04073023>.
- Quintanilla Raso, M. C. (2004). Propiedad vinculada y enajenaciones: métodos y lógicas nobiliarias en la Castilla tardomedieval. *Historia. Instituciones. Documentos*, 31, 493-510.
- Quintanilla Raso, M. C. (2006). Identidad y patrimonio. Salvaguarda y transmisión en las casas nobiliarias castellanas a finales del Medievo. La casa condal de la Puebla del Maestre. *En la España medieval*, N.º Extra, 157-183.
- Rodrigues, J. D. (2002). A Casa como modelo organizacional das nobrezas de São Miguel (Açores) no século XVIII. *História: Questões & Debates*, 36, 11-28.
- Rodrigues, J. D. (2013). Endogamia, consanguinidade e reprodução social: o mercado matrimonial das elites açorianas no Antigo Regime. In C. Santos & P. T. Matos (eds.), *A demografia das sociedades insulares portuguesas. Séculos XV a XXI* (p. 201-219). Braga: CITCEM.
- Rodríguez Pérez, R. (2012). Los conflictos intrafamiliares de la casa de los Vélez (1546-1567). *Chronica nova: Revista de historia moderna de la Universidad de Granada*, 38: 243-268.
- Rosa, M. L. (1988). Imagem física, saúde mental e representação familiar: a exclusão de deficientes à sucessão de morgadio (instituições, legislação, literatura jurídica). In *Arqueologia do Estado. I Jornadas sobre formas de organização e exercício dos poderes da Europa do Sul, séculos XIII-XVIII* (vol. 2, p. 1059-1097). Lisboa: História & Crítica.
- Rosa, M. L. (1991). Quadros de organização do poder nobre na Baixa Idade Média. Estrutura familiar, patrimónios e percursos linhagísticos de quatro famílias de Portalegre. *A Cidade*, 4, 47-65.
- Rosa, M. L. (1995). *O Morgadio em Portugal, sécs. XIV-XV. Modelos e práticas de comportamentos linhagísticos*. Lisboa: Editorial Estampa.
- Rosa, M. L. (1996). Mariage et empêchements canoniques de parenté dans la société portugaise (1455-1520). *Mélanges de l'École française de Rome. Moyen Âge*, 108 (2), 525-608.
- Rosa, M. L. (2012). *As Almas Herdeiras. Fundação de capelas fúnebres e afirmação da alma como Sujeito de Direito (Portugal, 1400-1521)*. Lisboa: Imprensa Nacional - Casa da Moeda.
- Rosa, M. L. (2017). Reconstruindo a produção, documentalização e conservação da informação organizacional pré-moderna. Perspectivas teóricas e proposta de percurso de investigação. *Boletim do Arquivo da Universidade de Coimbra*, 30, 547-586.
- Rosa, M. L. (2019). The Production of Genealogical Knowledge for the Arrangement of Archives of Noble Families (Portugal, Fifteenth to Early Nineteenth Centuries). In J. Eickmeyer, M. Friedrich & V. Bauer (eds.), *Genealogical Knowledge in the Making*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110593518-013>.

- Rosa, M. L. (2020). Preventing Household Failure: Figures of Authority in Familial Corporate Bodies (The Portuguese Morgadio System from the Fourteenth to the Seventeenth Century). *L'Atelier du Centre de recherches historiques*, 22. <https://doi.org/10.4000/acrh.11096>.
- Ruiz, T. F. (2015). *Discursos de sangre y parentesco en Castilla durante la Baja Edad Media y la Época Moderna*. Santander: Universidad de Cantabria.
- Sabeau, D. W., & Teuscher, S. (2007). Kinship in Europe: a new approach to long term development. In D. W. Sabeau, S. Teuscher & J. Mathieu (eds.), *Kinship in Europe: approaches to long-term development (1300-1900)* (p. 1-32). New York/Oxford: Berghahn Books.
- Sáinz de Rozas, M. P. (1991). La pervivencia de las estrategias «vinculares» en las transmisiones testamentarias de la segunda mitad del siglo XIX: el caso del marquesado de Grañina, 1850-1875. In P. Saavedra & R. Villares Paz (coord.), *Señores y campesinos en la Península Ibérica, siglos XVIII-XX. Simposio internacional de historia rural, siglos XVIII-XX* (vol. 1, p. 38-61). S. L.: Crítica.
- Soria Mesa, E. (2002). Las capellanías en la Castilla moderna: familia y ascenso social. In A. Irigoyen López & A. L. Pérez Ortiz (coord.), *Familia, transmisión, y perpetuación (siglos XVI-XIX)* (p. 135-148). Murcia: Universidad de Murcia.
- Soria Mesa, E. (2004). Genealogía y poder. Invención de la memoria y ascenso social en la España Moderna. *Estudis: Revista de historia moderna*, 30, 21-56
- Soria Mesa, E. (2007). *La nobleza en la España Moderna: cambio y continuidad*. Madrid: Marcial Pons.
- Sottomayor-Pizarro, J. A. (2013). A chefia da linhagem aristocrática (sécs. XII-XIV). Reflexões em torno de uma prática idealizada. *Studia Zamorensia*, 12, 27-40.
- Sottomayor-Pizarro, J. A. (2016). A Coroa e a aristocracia em Portugal, sécs. XII-XV. Uma relação de serviço?. In *Discurso, memoria y representación. La nobleza peninsular en la Baja Edad Media: Actas de la XLII Semana de Estudios Medievales* (p. 141-176).
- Sousa, B. V. (2013). Afirmção Social e Liderança Nobiliárquica em Portugal (Séculos XIII-XV). *Studia Zamorensia*, 12, 41-55.
- Teixeira, A. (2003). O Tratado de Morgados, de Manuel Álvares Pegas: Uma fonte histórica olvidada. En J. Ascensão et al. (Coord.), *Estudos em homenagem ao Prof. Doutor Raúl Ventura* (Vol. 2, pp. 1195-1281). Faculdade de Direito da Universidade de Lisboa.
- Yun-Casalilla, B. (1998). From political and social management to economic management? Castilian aristocracy and economic development, 1450-1800. In C. E. Núñez (ed.), *Aristocracy, patrimonial management strategies and economic development, 1450-1800* (pp. 55-68). Secretariado de Publicaciones de la Universidad de Sevilla.